

New perspectives on Malay as the Indonesian lingua franca : Comparison to English as global language

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Introduction

When asked what the main function of language is, most people will say that language is a tool used to learn or gather information on topics such as computing or astronomy. In other words, language is needed to enable us to find out “things” about the world. While such a function of language may explain the thriving role of language, it does not tell us why it spreads, dies, multiplies, colonizes, and rejuvenates, or why it sometimes is used as a lingua franca (LF). Information is more likely to be digested upon reflection rather than through interaction. So the “best” answer here as to the primary function of language is that it is a device for social bonding rather than information gathering. In this study, language is viewed instrumentally, and its social interactional capacity enables it to have far-reaching sociopolitical implications (Dunbar, 2003). This social interactional phenomena does not only take place within close networks such as families, friends, and neighbors for before long, populations expand and people will feel the need to communicate beyond these immediate networks due to extended purposes. The world we live in has long been a multilingual and multicultural one, and hence people are tempted, constantly, to break down language barriers so as to create a common medium of communication. To do this, new languages are then created or existing languages made to fulfill this communicative function.

It is generally accepted that the use of English has spread around the world. This spread is a result of two major strands of expansion. Historically, British colonization efforts have led to English being transported from Britain to territories around the globe. A second, more contemporary motor to this spread is the growing use of English as a lingua franca in contexts where people of different lingua cultural backgrounds meet and communicate. It is this latter development that has spawned a great deal of research on English as a lingua franca (ELF) as of lately.

The use of English in contexts where speakers from various national cultures get into contact with each other is certainly not a new phenomenon. However, the greater visibility of such contacts, for example as an outcome of increasing “Europeanisation”, has recently caused many linguists to devote a great deal of their attention to such transnational uses of English. This has led to a greater institutional recognition of uses of English that widely depart from more traditional notions of nativeness and standard-orientation. A result of this development is that scholars’ reasoning about the status of English in Europe has taken on various shapes, ranging from more traditional to more innovative approaches. Among these four positions, there are two traditional approaches that have lost ground as of recently and can therefore be described as largely historical phases in the treatment of English in Europe. This is the case for the *linguistic imperialism approach* to English in Europe and *the Euro-English debate*. The two remaining strands, *the English as a lingua franca approach* and *the postmodernist reconceptualisation of English* have become more prominent in recent years and accordingly play a major role in contemporary discussions of English in Europe.

Discussions

An explanation for the fact that English is not a “killer language” that works to the detriment of other European languages is given by House (2003). House takes into account the function of a certain language in people’s lives and makes a distinction between *languages of identification* and *languages of communication*. On the one hand, a speaker’s L1 serves as a language of ethnic/national identification. English as a foreign language, on the other hand, generally fulfills the pragmatic function of communicating with people outside one’s speech community and is therefore a language of communication. As each of these two language types is connected to a different function, they are

unlikely to compete and can therefore exist side by side without one encroaching on the domains of the other (Lüdi, 2002). According to this reasoning, ELF as a language of communication does not pose a threat to European national languages, which are considered languages of identification.

Makoni and Pennycook (2007) have suggested more explicitly that the notion of “a language” is the product of discursive construction. They show that much of contemporary linguistics is affected by a meta discursive regime that treats languages as clearly bounded and therefore countable entities. Labels like “English” or “French”, for example, suggest that the entities they denote can be clearly separated. But if one looks at the history of these two “languages”, one finds that they are not as separate as would be thought. During the Middle Ages, French extensively influenced English, especially on the lexical level. This has even led some linguists to suggest that Middle English is a French-based creole (Curzan, 2003). More recently, French has experienced a strong influx of English vocabulary, which language purists in France had initially failed to curb by proscribing the use of English words in public domains. After all, both varieties are descendants from one and the same source, namely *Proto-Indo-European*. Therefore, a representation of French and English as clearly separate entities is too simplistic. An alternative description would be that French is a component of English and vice versa or that French and English share a large part of their resources. Purist language policies such as evident in France aim at making language conform to the dominant nationalized discourse.

The considerations of the Euro-English strand of work are heavily influenced by Kachru’s (1985) classic model of the three concentric circles of World Englishes. It categorizes Englishes in relation to acquisition patterns, domains, standardization and, most significantly, by nation. *Inner circle Englishes* (English as a native language; ENL) are spoken as L1 in countries where English is the default medium for private communication, often by monolingual white speakers as the descendants of the first English diaspora wave coming from the British Isles. These Englishes (e.g. BrE, AmE, AusE, NZE) are well codified and standardized and generally provide norms for foreign language learners of English.

Outer circle Englishes are used as second official languages (English as a second language; ESL) in countries that have a historical relation to the former British Empire (e.g. India, Nigeria, Singapore) and are therefore associated with the second wave diaspora. They usually form a component in speakers’ multilingual repertoires and are as a consequence influenced by the speakers’ local L1s. Besides education, they tend to be restricted to such domains as administration and government. In multilingual societies, they are often used as an *intranational lingua franca*, because they are perceived to be neutral in the sense that they do not privilege any of the indigenous ethnic groups. However, from a historical point of view, it is difficult to claim that the use of English, i.e. the language of the former colonizers, is a neutral medium of communication. Outer circle Englishes are typically in a process of developing their own linguistic norms, thereby emancipating themselves from BrE as the normative reference point.

Finally, *expanding circle Englishes* are said to be spoken in all countries that lack a British colonial past. In these, English is acquired as a foreign language (EFL), i.e. typically through active language learning in formal education. English is here primarily learnt for purposes of international communication (for example, in politics, science or tertiary education) and does not normally fulfil official functions on the national level. Expanding circle Englishes have (so far) not developed local norms and therefore depend on inner circle varieties as exonormative standards. In terms of speaker numbers, expanding circle Englishes are clearly dominant, and this dominance is likely to increase as more and more people around the world learn English as a foreign language. This development raises consequential questions concerning the legitimate “ownership” of the language, which was traditionally seen to be in the hands of the native speakers (Widdowson, 1994)

Kachru’s circle model has been highly influential and its terminology has proven to be a practical tool for discussing the use of English around the world. However, this very practicality is also an aspect that can easily be criticized in the face of complex local sociolinguistics realities (Bruthiaux, 2003; Jenkins, 2003; Park & Wee, 2009; Pennycook, 2003; Saraceni, 2010; Yano, 2009). For example, it is problematic that the three circle categories cover up (often fundamental) intra-circle diversity and that the model does not allow for any flexibility in the handling of the circles, which would be

required, for example, for countries that show characteristics of more than one circle category. On the one hand, many outer circle countries today have a significant number of native English speakers. On the other hand, immigration to inner circle societies has led to the presence of numerous ESL speakers. A well-known example of a country that cannot be that easily categorized is South Africa (Bruthiaux, 2003; Park & Wee, 2009), which exhibits a high degree of heterogeneity in the Englishes used, ranging from White South African English (which would actually qualify as an inner circle variety) to Black South African and South African Indian English (which share more characteristics with outer circle Englishes) to EFL (traditionally located in the expanding circle). Furthermore, an approach that divides countries up into three macro circles is not able to deal with the fact that written norms across the three circles differ relatively little from each other compared to spoken usage (Bruthiaux, 2003).

For this very reason, Park and Wee (2009) have set out to reconceptualise the circles model. Instead of treating it as a tool for the description of sociolinguistics realities, they take it to be a model that deals with dominant ideologies in relation to the use of English around the world and stereotypical correlations between a country's sociopolitical history and the local status of English. Moreover, they connect the circles model to Bourdieu's theorisation of the *linguistic market*. As a result, inner circle Englishes are said to obtain their high value on the global linguistic market through an indexical association with powerful speaker groups, whereas expanding circle Englishes carry the least prestige. With respect to identity matters, Park and Wee (2009) contrast an essentialist model that assumes a stable, and therefore constraining, relationship between language and (especially national) identity with what they call an "artful performance model", i.e. a model that values crossing and subversion of such normative identity discourses and treats questions of authenticity as irrelevant. The original circles model expects inner circle speakers to be highly proficient and authentic users who construct their (national) belonging through English. In the expanding circle, by contrast, the use of English is expected to be inauthentic, instrumental, of low proficiency and a sign of disloyalty to national affiliations. If one took the actual proficiency of speakers into account, it would be impossible to come up with such a macro-category model as Kachru's, because many speakers would then have to be placed outside of the circle to which their nation has been assigned (Yano, 2009).

The term *lingua franca* (as opposed to variety) does not denote a certain structural configuration but rather refers to language use for a certain communicative purpose, namely intercultural communication. It is not associated with particular groups of language users and, therefore, leaves it open who the legitimate "owners" of a language are or whether it can in fact be owned by anybody. The term challenges more traditional thinking, according to which the native speakers of a certain variety are considered its only authentic users.

As native speakers regularly form the minority in ELF communication, it is questionable whether ELF should be measured against a nativespeaker norm. Compared to other terms describing the use of English around the globe (English as an International Language, International English, Global English), which are associated with a privileging of inner and outer circle Englishes, the relatively new designation English as a *lingua franca* according to Jenkins (2007) has significant advantages. It suggests communication between speakers of different L1s and a tolerance of L1 influence on the use of English. Furthermore, it places greater emphasis on commonalities rather than inter-variety differences and views non-native speakers as the driving force behind developments in contemporary uses of English. ELF is shaped in use by transculturation processes, obtaining its hybridity from what has traditionally been called L1 substrate influence as well as mechanisms of accommodation and meaning negotiation. In other words, – and in contrast to essentialist claims of Anglophone linguistic imperialism – what is currently spreading around the world is neither BrE nor AmE, but local adaptations of English (Mukherjee, 2008; Widdowson, 1997).

The study of English as a *lingua franca* originated in the context of the World Englishes paradigm. As Seidlhofer (2009a) discusses at length, the ELF and World Englishes paradigms have a number of common concerns that may be said to unite them as partners challenging more traditional approaches to ELT, which see native English usage patterns (usually BrE or AmE) as target "standards" (Cogo, 2008; Jenkins, 2007). While World Englishes research has fostered the emancipation of outer circle Englishes, the motivation of ELF researchers to empower non-native speakers has not stopped

at the outer boundaries of the outer circle. Expanding circle users are also seen as practising a legitimate form of English that neither needs to depend on an exonormative native standard nor does it need to establish its own endonormative standard. In fact, ELF communication weakens the traditional connection between language use and linguistic normativity. Both the World Englishes and the ELF approach celebrate the linguistic diversity within “English” and have generally taken multilingualism as the norm (for example, by favoring bilingual teachers or taking the competent L2 speaker as a role model). Both share a decentralizing agenda that questions native speakers as the (only) legitimate owners of English (Saraceni, 2010).

Jenkins (2007) is also concerned with the many kinds of misconceptions that have arisen from the reception of ELF research (Seidlhofer, 2006). For example, it is false that ELF research has proposed replacing ENL as a teaching model. ELF researchers have merely promoted ELF as a potential alternative to native speaker norms without demanding the abolition of the latter. Their ultimate aim is to put learners in the position to make an informed choice whether they would like to aim at ENL (i.e. as in the traditional ELT approach), which is best suited for communication with native speakers of English, or at ELF, which would be an alternative for those who aim at successful international communication, often with other non-native speakers.

As the traditional variety concept is inadequate for a description of ELF, Seidlhofer (2009) suggests a reconceptualisation of linguistic variation as a process rather than as a matter of varieties as abstract states of usage. Instead of reintroducing homogeneity (a criticism sometimes voiced by World Englishes scholars as representatives of the heterogeneity position), the spread of ELF in fact causes linguists to conceptualize linguistic diversity in an alternative way to variety pluralization, namely as subject to contextual fluidity (Cogo, 2008; Otsuji & Pennycook, 2010).

The conceptualization of English in the postmodern age can be seen as a reaction to modernist theorisations of “languages” as nation-bound, codified and standardized systems that can be taught as foreign languages to non-native speakers, who in turn need to orient to native speakers as authorities of correctness (Graddol, 2006). In a world in which national structures increasingly have to face competition from transnational discourses, linguistic concepts that are based on the traditional notion of “a language” become less relevant for the description of linguistic practices. The recent strengthening of Europe as a transnational concept as well as of ELF as a language use that defies variety status can therefore be considered as two sides of the same coin

Postmodernist discussions of the role of English in trans cultural flows aim at a reconceptualisation of the notion of “language”, or at least at a questioning of its usefulness when it is applied to English. In such discussions, “languages” are considered as discursive formations evolving in language use rather than as abstract language systems (in the Saussurean or Chomskyan sense) that are reflected or instantiated in actual language use. In fact, the very distinction between langue and parole collapses in the light of post structuralist thinking, because the latter treats the language system as the result of processes of discursive materialization (Hornscheidt, 1998). Grammatical structures in this view have reached their substance through on-going recitation in language use. It is this substance that grammarians try to describe. However, post structuralist conceptualizations like these have not yet entered mainstream linguistics to a significant extent, even though procedural approaches to language are not new. Hopper, for example, has proposed a theory of ‘emergent grammar’ (Hopper 1998; Fox 2007), in which the language system is not described as a stable entity in the heads of (native) speakers but rather as taking shape in linguistic practices. The formation of a “language” then takes place performatively through on-going repetition and imitation of communicative acts that finally lead to the sedimentation of those communicative behaviors that have proven to remain in common usage.

Finally, some writers have suggested connections between the spread of English and more general issues in global relations. Ndebele (1987) suggests that 'the spread of English went parallel with the spread of the culture of international business and technological standardization'. Naysmith (1987) argues that English language teaching 'has become part of the process whereby one part of the world has become politically, economically and culturally dominated by another' (p. 3). The core of this process, he argues, is the 'central place 7the English language has taken as the language of

international capitalism' (ibid.). Such a position, which suggests that English is an integral part of the global structures of dependency, has been explored at length by Robert Phillipson (1988; 1992). Phillipson's aim is to establish a connection between imperialism in general - global structural relations that maintain and reproduce economic and other inequalities between countries - and what he calls 'English linguistic imperialism'. English linguistic imperialism, a sub type of general linguistic imperialism, operates when 'The dominance of English is asserted and maintained by the establishment and continuous reconstitution of structural and cultural inequalities between English and other languages' (1992)

The official promotion of English as the sole working language of ASEAN has provided great impetus to its rapid development as a regional lingua franca. In addition, therefore, to the usual motivations to use English, namely to be able to participate in and benefit from modernization and globalization, its official status in ASEAN provides an extra motivation for the teaching and learning of English. The role of English as a lingua franca across ASEAN is not, of course, unique. The major role of English in today's world is as a lingua franca. That is to say English is most commonly used as a lingua franca by people who are multilingual and for whom English is a shared language. In ASEAN, English is typically used as a lingua franca by ASEAN multilingual for whom English is an additional language. Thus, for example, Thais, Indonesians, Filipinos and Vietnamese will typically use English as a lingua franca with each other. This has implications for the development of English. As Mauranen (2006) has pointed out, with English as a lingua franca becoming the most common role of English in today's world, we need to know something about it; how it is developing and how it is being shaped and used by speakers of ELF.

Historical Lingua Francas, Trade and Commerce : Malay of Indonesian origin

Another context where the use of lingua franca is felt keenly is that of trade and commerce. In a study of trade and commerce, one notices that Western Asian and northeastern African societies have so much in common in their technology and other cultural aspects that it can only be assumed that there was some degree of intercommunication through the use of a variety of lingua francas, the names of which are now lost to antiquity (Trigger, 1993)

The natural habitat of lingua francas are roads, rivers, and ports, since the act of moving goods from one place to another means that people who transported the goods had not only to establish cordial relations but also to communicate in great detail through the use of a lingua franca with those along the way. Doubtless cities, which were most amenable to language shifts, were the societies most accessible to reinvention, either being on the main overland or riverine trading routes (Frank and Gills, 1993). For example, it was along the River Congo that Lingala spread as the lingua franca for trade, and it was from port to port that Malay became the lingua franca of Indonesia. Swahili (meaning "coasts" in Arabic), used from East to West Africa, and initially a sailor's language, spread in the same way, predominantly at the fairs and marketplaces along these coastlines where people exchanged foodstuffs and where quantities of goods from long distance were displayed. The people who were adept in using lingua francas were usually groups specialized in exchange—merchants (Olsen, 2002).

With full-scale commerce came commercial specialists who would move from their home community and settle either as aliens or settlers in the trading town. These traders would be fluent linguists, adept with the lingua franca(s) of trade and speaking their mother tongue in more private domains. Languages such as Arabic, German, Hausa, and Armenian became widely spoken outside their homelands because of such trading specialists. The communities in which they settled could then serve as cross-cultural language brokers, helping and encouraging trade between the host society and people of their own origin who moved along the trade routes. As time went on, this process became more complex—what began as a single settlement grew to a series of trade settlements to what may be called more aptly "trade diasporas" (Curtin, 1984). Here, a process of "infiltration" (Ostler, 2006) a combination of both migration and diffusion is discernible. Migration results when a language community moves bodily, bring their new language along with it; diffusion results where speakers of one community, because they do not live in large numbers, come to assimilate their language to that of another with whom they are in contact (e.g., colonialization).

Other trade diasporas left a legacy in the form of cultural and linguistic minorities in foreign lands even if these minorities no longer devoted themselves to long-distance trade. For example, the beginnings of Chinese settlement in Southeast Asia go back to trade diasporas that started to operate in the first centuries AD though they were later supplemented by contract laborers and other immigrants (Suryadinata, 2004). They kept their Chinese languages and spoke a LF such as Swahili, Lingala, Arabic, and Malay, with their own distinctive accent, which in turn influenced the native speech communities they passed through. *Baba Malay* (sometimes called the Creole Chinese) is a result of early male Hokien trade emigrants to Malacca who found themselves in a predominantly Malay-speaking environment and were thus forced to gradually abandon their Hokien mother tongue and to learn Malay to survive in the early 17th century. Their subsequent intermarriages with local Malay women also led them to develop a special sub-variety of the Malay language after one or two generations of local born descents (Jürgen, 1998). However, in the 20th century, some of these overseas Chinese no longer ran a trade diaspora, though they kept much of their commercial tradition and still tended to dominate wholesale and retail trade (Watson, 2005). Besides in Southeast Asia, similar communities can also be found in Tanzania, Kenya, and Uganda. Their commercial importance dates only from the 19th century, but they dominated the retail trade of all three colonies until the coming of independence (Manning, 2005).

Another context where lingua franca unfolds itself is when the colonizer meets the colonized. According to Firth (1937), lingua francas are made not by grammarians but by world powers. For example, the rise in English as the predominant lingua franca in the world today is not surprising when we take into account the fact that throughout history, the distribution of languages in the world has reflected the distribution of power in the world. So too, the most widely spoken languages—English, Mandarin, Spanish, French, Arabic, and Russian—are or were the languages of imperial states that actively promoted the use of their languages by other peoples.

Slavery is a byproduct of empires and hence is part of the story of lingua francas. Their offspring were fluent in multiple languages and had complex identities. They spoke pidgin and later, creole, in various shades and colors. While they could be identified by language, birthplace, nation or skin color, none of these categories provided an absolute identity. Similarly, slavery expanded in Southeast Asia in the 18th and 19th centuries. The captive populations came not so much from South Asia but from the Indonesian islands. Indonesian slavery expanded as local and Dutch planters in Java, Melaka, and Ceylon (now Sri Lanka) purchased slaves and put them to work on plantations for coffee, spices, and sugar. These slaves would then learn to speak the lingua franca of the region, a patois known as *Bazaar Malay*, which still thrives today in rural areas and among the less educated segments of the populace. Interestingly, unlike in America, the slave-descended population was not segregated but was assimilated socially, biologically, and linguistically into the free population. So too their patois continued to be assimilated into Javanese, Standard Malay, and Singhalese (Boomgaard, 2001)

Finally, the world “nation” has gone through a number of substantial changes. It is derived from the Latin noun, “nation,” which means “stock” or “breed.” In medieval universities, “nations” were the quarters in which students of various origins were lodged, according to their places of origin. In the Oxford Dictionary of the 19th century, the word nation is defined as a “distinct race or people characterized by common descent, language or history, usually organized as a separate political state and occupying a definite territory.” The definition of territoriality or common descent and then emphasize the “radical,” “novel,” and “modern” nature of nationalist consciousness (Anderson, 1991). Hence, for the first time in history, theoretically at least, the nationalistic new world order enabled class, region, family, sex, and color to become irrelevant to citizenship. A nation is a group of people held together by a shared loyalty, history, and identity to a bill of rights or a constitution of sorts. These rights and duties are laid down formally in writing—in state declarations or common law, the underlying assumption being that these are codifications of the national will, expressing the shared pattern of values and traditions of the community. On a more material level, it is also a “modern institution” and “a highly organized territorial political unit with a centralized authority administering in a methodical and systematic manner the affairs of a common people through a large bureaucracy of government department” (Hobsbawn, 1992). In brief, “nation” can be said to comprise a “sovereign people” bound together with common political sentiment and a unitary consciousness of identity (Greenfeld, 1992; Gellner, 1983).

The heyday or climax of nationalism can be said to be between the 17th to the 19th centuries, when European nations managed to conquer and share large parts of the world, such as the city-states of Southeast Asia and the tribal areas of Africa. Ironically, when it was no longer fashionable to be a colonizer at the end of the World War II, every former colony at the inception of its liberation from the Western powers wanted to follow the order of “nationhood,” As the emergent new order was amorphous and as yet indistinct, being only in its formative stages, care was taken by newly independent colonies to reinvent themselves after their Western masters with elaborate “trappings” of nationhood—a capital city, a head of state, a national anthem, a state crest, an army, a national airline, a national costume, a national language, a national flag, and a national state ideology. It was believed that the national word order would unite the diverse citizenry, as it had done in the past, in a “national will,” thereby laying the foundation stone for peace, progress, and prosperity (Chew, 2013).

But with the rise of the nation-state and the introduction of schooling, the rule altered and “horizontal transmission” begins to occur, where people are trained in the school language. In addition, something happens not possible before: Languages can be deliberately and effectively replaced sometimes during the span of only a few generations, usually by order and sometimes by choice (Chew, 2013 ; Gupta, 1989). A case in point is *Sumpah Pemuda 1928* with the promotion of a language to official lingua franca status in a nation (Rahman, 2008 ; Sneddon, 2004 ; Anderson, 1991) .

Conclusion

In brief, lingua francas originated and developed through contact and accommodation in villages, city-states, and nations. They spread through the exchanges among people within a community, the episodes of colonialization by small family groups, or the occasional flights of a whole community from overpopulation or disaster. Most of the lingua francas in human history can trace their origins back as languages of commerce and trade. Some began as pidgins, progressing on to becoming creoles and later vernaculars and national languages in their own right. Some have faded away. Those that have remained have adapted themselves well to contexts of change in their encounters with new speakers of the language.

While some linguists may desire to view all languages as intrinsically equal, the process of evolution has deemed that some languages are more equal than others. Evolution has also enabled some languages to live a far longer time than others, being spoken by important historical personages and larger populations. This in part is due to languages’ uncanny ability to adapt to circumstances and to align themselves with powerful forces. Others unfortunately are born and may die in obscurity.

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